

A Short Review- Use of Cyclodextrin for Insect Repellent Textiles

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Abstract:

Now a day, for better health personal hygiene is essential, in this regard manufacturing of specialty value-added textiles are booming. Numerous essential oils and aqueous extracts of some plants are encapsulated during textile finishes. Several compounds have been utilized such silica, melamine formaldehyde and urethanes by scientist as protective layer for controlled release. In addition to these above mentioned techniques, cyclodextrins (CDs) are been effectively utilized in textile finishes.

Keywords: cyclodextrin, electrospinning, functional, mosquito-repellency, micro-encapsulation

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1. Introduction:

Textile finishes can be classified into two classes, viz., functional and aesthetic. The functional finishes are intentionally applied to alter properties like durability, care, and comfort. By using chemical wet processing methods functional finishes can be achieved. Common functional finishes are antimicrobial, durable press antistatic, UV protection, flame retardant, self-cleaning, water repellent, soil-resistant, and wrinkle recovery [1].

Aesthetic finishes intensify the fabric apparel properties. They can modify the surface, luster, texture, and drape of textile substrates. Both mechanical and chemical methods can be used to impart such finish; mechanical processes can place greater emphasis on this finishing [2].

Insects have numerous applications that can be considered both beneficial and harmful to human beings and they have a considerable involvement in human life. If we focus on harmfulness of insects then we realize that they transfer many diseases, which may adversely affect human life. Besides these they can potentially damages the agricultural products and materials also [3].

Insect such as mosquitoes, flies, ticks, fleas, lice, ants, chiggers, etc. causes skin irritation, swelling, pain and illness to humans after being bitten [4]. In addition, insects may transfer parasites and pathogens that can disperse numerous diseases to human after biting them. These insects become the vector for annihilating disease pathogens such as malaria, dengue, and yellow fever [5]. Pathogens and parasites are responsible of vector-borne diseases among human beings. Vectors are living creatures such as parasitical bugs that outspread the infective diseases either among mankind or from animal to mankind. They suck pathogens along with blood from an infected host (human/animal) and subsequently infuse it into another host. Among the many other Mosquitoes are popular examples of vector [6].

It is found that every single year, more than 500 million people around the globe infected with malaria [7]. Most of the cases leads to death of infected people due to lack of awareness, financial conditions, polluted environment etc. These infectious diseases not only found in sub-Saharan Africa, but also in Asia, Latin America, parts of Europe, Middle East and Pacific countries. In addition to this it is observed that the global existence of dengue has been accelerated in recent decades [8]. If we notice that there are more than 3000 species of mosquito, however some of them leads to death and diseases, viz., Anopheles, Aedes and Culex etc.

Ticks are external parasites, living by consumption of the blood of mammals, birds, and sometimes reptiles and amphibians. Tick responsible for diseases which include various diseases such as Lyme disease (most common in United States country) [9], Crimean–Congo hemorrhagic fever, tularemia, babesiosis, ehrlichiosis, Bourbon virus,

bovine anaplasmosis and the Heartland virus [10]. Flea, the commonly known as *Siphonaptera*, comprises more than 2,500 species which live as external parasites of mammals and birds. Fleas outspread the plague [11] among rodents as well as potentially transfer the various disease to humans when they suck their blood [12].

Ants are common around the world, with the largest populations found in rain forests. The sting of jack jumper ants can be lethal for humans [13] while Fire ant stings can result in severe symptoms such as chest pains, nausea, and dizziness to shock, and occasionally cases, coma [14]. For protection against the biting harmful insects, protective clothing is most effective and convenient way to covers most of the human body. There are numerous kinds of insect-repellent products such as sprays, body lotions, stickers, and even wristbands available in the market. Insect-repellent textiles need to be effective long-lasting after multiple washes. Insecticides are the chemical substance used to kill or repel insects. There are two types of insecticides being utilized most one is repellent insecticides another is contact insecticides.

Repellent insecticides repel insects and pests instead of causing their death however contact insecticides comprise the neurotoxins which make insects and pests unconscious when they come in contact [15]. Repellent insecticides force the arthropod (insects and pests) to move away from the host by preventing the activeness of arthropod's sensors and confuse them.

Insect repellents generally classified into two sub classes, (1) Synthetic chemicals and (2) Natural chemicals most of which are oils extracted from various plants such as citronella, lemon, eucalyptus, and permethrin [16]. The importance of insect repellents for human use is very essential, since there are very few vaccines are available as prevention measure and treatment of any disease is also not very cost effective. Hence it become necessary to induce insecticidal chemical finishing textiles and clothing works [17].

It is well known fact that good personal hygiene is very necessary for better health. In this regards inventions and research is been carried out by scientist world-wide and definitely will be carry out in future also [18]. Now a days specialty value-added textiles, such as aromatic textiles [19] are flourishing [20]. Numerous essential oils and aqueous extracts of some plants widely employed in different fields [21]. However, these oils or extract are need to be coated / encapsulated during textile finishes hence, due their high volatility and chemical instability the finishing applied is never long lasting and its effectiveness fades away very soon [22]. In this regards several compounds have been utilized to tackle the above mentioned problem such silica, melamine formaldehyde and urethanes by scientist [23]. In addition to these above mentioned techniques, cyclodextrins (CDs) are been effectively utilized in textile finishes [24].

Cyclodextrins are cyclic oligosaccharides, comprising 5 or more α -D-glucopyranose units linked with 1-4 glycosidic bond [25]. In general CDs contain six to eight units of glucopyranose in a ring form viz., α -CD, β -CD and γ -CD (Figure 1) [26] forming toroid and bucket like structure.

Figure 1: Various forms of structures of cyclodextrins

Textile industry is very sensitive towards the price of the finished product in market. The cost effective raw materials and methods are always encouraged by this industry and hence β -CD used more in various applications than α -CD, and γ -CD.

2. History of Cyclodextrin

The great scientist M. A. Villiers about 130 years ago (**1891**) isolated crystalline compounds by digesting the starch with *Bacillus amylobacter*, having composition to be $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ which subsequently verified to be a cyclodextrin. Initially, M. A. Villiers called these products “cellulosine”, due to their resemblance in chemical and physical properties of cellulose. Further, twelve years later, Schardinger, was able to separate two crystalline products, dextrins **A** and **B**, which were described as "Schardinger sugars". Further, few more scientist contribute in this research area [27].

3. Cyclodextrins (CDs)

3.1 Properties of Cyclodextrins

The central cavity of cyclodextrin is hydrophobic in nature than the outer surface which is hydrophilic due to -OH (hydroxyl groups). The larger opening of cyclodextrin contains the secondary hydroxyl groups while towards the smaller openings primary hydroxyl groups are present (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Pictorial presentation of toroid structure and hydrophobic cavity of CD

The three common CDs (α , β , and γ -CD) were profoundly studied [28]. Though the δ -CD have nine glucopyranose units in ring form it was proved that the δ -CD did not show any major solubilization effect on sparingly soluble chemicals in water with some exemptions. The larger CDs are having collapsed structure in which their actual cavity smaller than α , β , and γ -CD, hence not suitable to form inclusion complex with guest molecules (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: Schematic presentation of “Collapsed cylinder” structure of the δ -CD [29]

Due to more solubility of α -CD and γ -CD in aqueous solution than β -CD it is very difficult to isolate both α -CD and γ -CD during their formation which leads to easy availability of β -CD along and inexpensive in market. Hence β -CD is first choice of scientist to use it and explore it. The various physical and chemical properties of CDs are tabulated (Table 1).

Table 1 - The various physical and chemical properties [30] of cyclodextrins

Sr. No.	Property	Cyclodextrin		
		α	β	γ
1	Glucose units	6	7	8
2	Empirical formula (anhydrous)	$C_{36}H_{60}O_{30}$	$C_{42}H_{70}O_{35}$	$C_{48}H_{80}O_{40}$
3	Mol wt (anhydrous)	972.85	1134.99	1297.14
4	Cavity length, Å	8	8	8
5	Cavity diameter, Å (approx)	~5.2	~6.6	~8.4
6	Approx volume of the cavity, Å ³	174	262	427
7	Solubility (water, 25°), Mol L ⁻¹	0.1211	0.0163	0.168
8	Water of Hydration	~6.0	~12.0	~13.0

3.2 Inclusion complex formation

The cyclodextrins form inclusion complexes (host–guest complexes) with a very wide range of solid, liquid and gaseous compounds without any breaking or making of covalent bonds during formation [31]. The formation of inclusion complex with a guest molecule is depended on two key factors.

- The first is the relative size of the cyclodextrin to the size of the guest molecule. Wrong sized guest molecules will not fit properly into the cyclodextrin cavity.
- The second critical factor is the thermodynamic interactions among the cyclodextrin, guest and solvent. The favorable net energetic driving force pulls the guest into the cyclodextrin’s cavity and forms the host-guest complexation.

It is found that α -CD suitable to complex low molecular weight molecules or compounds such as aliphatic side chains, β -CD are capable of complexion the aromatics and heterocycles and γ -cyclodextrin can accommodate larger molecules such as macrocycles and steroids. Heating elevates the solubility of the complex but, destabilizes the complex. The heat stability of the complex varies with guest, most complexes are stable up to 50–60 °C, while strongly bounded or highly insoluble complex are stable at higher temperatures also. Water is the most ordinarily used medium in which complexation reactions can be carried out. The availability of CDs for complexation is depend upon the solubilization in provided solvent. Up to certain increased amount of water, the solubility of CDs increases which leads to ease of complexation. However, as the amount of water is increased further, the cyclodextrin and the guest do not get in contact easily which retards the rate of complexation. Volatile guests can be removed complexation by heating. With highly volatile guests, this can be prevented by using a sealed reactor or by refluxing the volatile guests back to the mixing vessel. This property allows to use the CDs for controlled release of guest molecules whenever required. Generally, host-guest complex is stable and having prolonged shelf life at ambient temperatures under moisture free conditions. Replacement of the guest by some other guest requires temperature change. In numerous instance, water can substitute the guest. The Vibrational Raman Optical Activity experimental evidence showed that CDs have conformation flexibility. The theoretical molecular dynamics studies indicate that the CDs are able to modify their shape in order to accommodate different guest molecules. In conclusion, cyclodextrins do not have a rigid truncated-cone structure and due to their flexibility, wide range of inclusion complex can be achieved [32].

4. Applications of Cyclodextrins

4.1 In Synthetic Chemistry

Cyclodextrins have been widely used in organic syntheses, due to its ability of forming inclusion complex with reactive partners and also some time they can catalyze chemical reactions with high selectivity as well as transfer hydrophobic molecules into aqueous medium [33].

4.2 In Pharmaceutical

CDs, are useful in pharmaceutical auxiliaries with versatile smart utility resulting from the inclusion of polymers, have been broadly used as drug delivery systems. Several CD's derivatives used as drug carriers and designed for potential use in a clinical trial. CD's able to form an assembly of cyclodextrin-based Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) which have the porous features of MOFs and to show encapsulation capability of CD for drug delivery. Recently cyclodextrin is successfully utilized in ocular drug delivery systems, including drug/CD complexes, in nanocarriers and microcarriers as nanoemulsions, nanoparticles, micelles, liposomes, nanosponges, microparticles, and microspheres. Additionally, cyclodextrin are found to be very applicative in formation of various hydrogels such as, supramolecular hydrogels, contact lenses etc., CD-based inserts are also developed by some scientists [34-35].

4.3 In Soil and fertilizer technology

Soil Bioremediation includes the use of living organisms to remediate polluted sites, and is cost-effective and environmentally benign remediation technique. Bioremediation of contaminants consist of various techniques such as bio-degradation using soil microorganisms, phytoremediation using plants, or vermiremediation using earthworms. In addition to these techniques CD's also can be utilized in soil bioremediation. Cyclodextrins (CD's) can be utilized as environmentally benign alternative to organic solvents or synthetic surfactant for growing organics bio-availability in soils. CD's forms inclusion complexes with pollutants which enhance its aqueous solubility and accelerating their bioremediation in soils. Especially hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (HPBCD) and randomly methylated- β -cyclodextrin (RAMEB) are being utilized due to due to their good water-solubility, biocompatibility, non-toxicity and moderate biodegradability. These CD's derivatives forms inclusion complexes with industrial chemicals waste and pesticides [36-37].

4.4 In Textile industry

5. Classification of Insect repellents

5.1 Synthetic Insect repellents

There is endless market demand for insect repellency in various material such as creams, sprays, non-volatile liquids, merchandising etc [38-39]. It is very difficult to full fill the market demand of insect repellency by using only natural insect repellents. The quality of most of the natural insect repellents can be compromised by various factor such as geographical conditions to grow the specific plants, consistency in active ingredient of isolated material from plant. In addition to these natural insect repellents are biodegradable and hence their activity may be diminished after some time. As being natural material we have to consider the environment factors also which can affect their availability.

All the above mentioned factors leads to invention of synthetic chemical which bears the anti-insect property. Some of the most used synthetic insect repellents are listed below [40],

- DEET,
- Picardin,
- Allethrin,
- Permethrin,
- Malathion.

The structure of the above mentioned synthetic insect repellents is as follows,

N,N-diethyl-3-methylbenzamide

(DEET)

1,2-di(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl *O,O*-dimethyl phosphorodithioate

(Malathion)

3-allyl-2-methyl-4-oxocyclopent-2-enyl 2,2-dimethyl-3-(2-methylprop-1-enyl)cyclopropanecarboxylate

(Allethrin)

3-phenoxybenzyl 3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylate

(Permethrin)

sec-butyl 2-(2-hydroxyethyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate

(Picaridin)

- *N,N*-Diethyl-*meta*-toluamide (DEET)

N,N-Diethyl-*meta*-toluamide commonly known as DEET [41] is one of the largely used the active ingredient insect repellent. Initially application of DEET was studied and effectively used by the US Army in 1946 and afterwards made available in public domain after 1957. The Environmental Protection Agency has patented over 230 DEET comprised products by more than 70 different companies around the various parts of world. DEET is largely utilized as a skin lotion, and its actions carry on for 4to 5 hours. If DEET coated on fabrics directly, it undergoes degradation under even gentle laundering conditions and hence it cannot be applied directly [42].

- Malathion

Malathion is an organophosphate pesticide and broadly applied in agriculture and human residential areas as pest control to achieve mosquito destruction. In some countries such as Australia and California, mixture of corn syrup and Malathion utilized to repel the Mediterranean fruit fly while in Australia it is still in use as anti-mosquito agent. In Canada and the United States, malathion was used against the West Nile virus [43].

- Allethrin

The Allethrin have low toxicity toward humans and the avian organisms. Allethrin used in some household insecticides such as RAID™ and mosquito coils. Though Allethrin is not deadly to adults, but is lethal to children. Addition to this it is lethal to fish and aquatic invertebrates [44].

- Permethrin

Permethrin is a class of pyrethroids [45], works against the target insect through contact or ingestion act as a mild insect repellent. Pyrethroids kills insects by making the nervous system hypersensitive to sensory stimuli. Permethrin has particularity against insects, and its *cis*-isomer has the maximum insecticidal activity. Merchandises treated with Permethrin and DEET together, to achieve effectual protection from mosquito-borne diseases such as malaria and dengue.

- Picaridin

Picaridin is not only efficient against mosquitoes and other insects, but also to a dermal irritant. The mode of action of picaridin is still unknown. Picaridin's harmful vapor inhibits the insect by affecting its taste and olfactory senses [46].

5.2 Natural Insect repellents

Some plant bears the active ingredient of insect repellency and can be extracted or isolated from roots, stems, leaves, flowers, fruits, or seeds. Most of these active ingredients are volatile oil in nature however, those are water soluble need to extracted in aqueous conditions. The major concern is regarding their controlled release mechanism during its use. Some important, easy available and easy to isolate natural mosquito repellents are listed below,

- Citronella oil,
- Castor oil,
- Clove oil,
- Eucalyptus oil,
- Cedar oil,
- Rosemary oil,
- Peppermint oil,
- Lemongrass oil,
- Geranium oil,

- Chrysanthemum oil.

Among the all above mentioned insect repellents, Chrysanthemum was found to be superior over the others in insect repellency action. Chrysanthemum shows its activity against mosquitoes for a prolonged period even after exposed to the environment [47].

Citronella oil can be effectively used for mood elevation during depression, deodorizing, sterilizing, and bug repelling. These essential oils can be applied onto cotton fabric by direct application, emulsion application, or micro-encapsulation application method [48]

6. Mechanism of repellent action

The insect repellency against blood-sucking insects such as mosquitoes can be classified into two variety based on the action pathways—

a) **Transpiration repellency** involves the sensory system of insects. In this category insects do not come in direct contact with surface treated with the active repellent ingredient. Repellent block insect's humidity sensory holes, which stops the moisture sensing capacity. Due to this insect unable to detect rise in atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations which is indication of human body around themselves.

b) **Direct repellency** involves the effect on peripheral nervous systems when contact is made by insect. Here the active ingredient forces the insect to avoid and not to touch (ward off) the treated surface before bloodsucking. The active ingredients such as DEET shows behavior-modification in insect and inhibits cholinesterase activity [49].

7. Evaluation methods for mosquito-repellency

The mosquito repellency need to be confirm and quantify using standard methods according to the WHO (World Health Organization) and the American Society for Testing Materials. There are few methods by performing them mosquito repellency can be evaluated. The more common test is Cage test, Cone test, Field test and Excito chamber test etc. Correct evaluation by using sophisticated analytical techniques is the most important aspect for any finished fabric. Scientist has contributed their ideas and construct some working models and testing methods to confirm and quantify mosquito repellency. The mosquito-repellency test was carried out by counting the number of insects landing on the arm covered with treated and untreated fabrics. The treated fabric presented the highest and the long-lasting protection against insects than the fabric sprayed with active ingredients [50].

7.1 Cone test

The cone test [51] is applied to measure the toxicity of insecticide treated bed nets against malaria, which is also capable to analyze the toxicity of other finished textiles. The standard WHO plastic cone was located on top of the treated surface of the sample and secured using a masking tape. Then five to ten female mosquitoes were blown inside the cone with aspirator and the mosquitoes were exposed to the treated surface. The numbers of mosquitoes resting on the treated samples were counted within a 3-min exposure. At the end of the exposure, the mosquitoes were transferred to the plastic cones for further observance. Next, a plastic cup was kept in an insecticide-free air furnished with 10% sucrose solution. The number of paralyzed test mosquitoes was determined 1 h later the exposition and the death rate was observed after 24 h. The mosquito repellency was measured using the following formula below,

$$\% \text{ Mosquito mortality} = \frac{(MR - MC)}{(100 - MC)} \times 100$$

Where, MR= the mosquitoes' mortality using a test replicate, MC = the mosquitoes' mortality using control samples.

7.2 Cage test

The cage is covered with transparent mosquito nets for easy measurement. It has holes in one side, covered with nets for the introduction of the arms of human subjects. Accordant to WHO accepted standards, the cage needs to be filled with 200 mosquitoes that have been starved all-night and only were provide with sucrose solution. Modify standards uses a lesser number of mosquitoes in the cage at least 30 mosquitoes, which provides high accuracy and better understanding of the typical biting behavior. Volunteers should not be active user of tobacco and should avoid use of fragrance or repellent products for 12 h before the test. The volunteer will insert left arm function as the control while the right arm as the testing of the treated specimen for a period of 3 min. If at least two mosquitoes landed or bite within the 3 min, the test will proceed. If there no mosquito lands within 3 min, the hand will be withdrawn from the cage. The number of mosquito landed counted independently with the digital

camera. The exposure is carried out in every 30 min up to 8 h or until the repellency fails. Each test sample was carried out in triplicate at $28\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $80\pm 5\%$ RH with a 5-min wait period between replicates. The time between use of the treated materials was registered as the protection time. The percentage of repellency or protection time was calculated using the formula below,

$$\% \text{ Mosquito protection} = \frac{(U - T)}{U} \times 100$$

Where, U = the number of mosquitoes on untreated samples or control samples and T = the number of mosquitoes on treated samples.

7.3 *Excito chamber method*

The mosquitoes were kept hungry overnight or for a minimum of 4 h before the test. The action of mosquitoes was observed in terms of the number of escaped mosquitoes (to another space) and mosquito's leftover inside the chamber which was filled with the activated mosquito repellent material. The measurement is registered after 10 and 30 min of influence. The test carried out in daylight and repeated four times. The percentage of mosquito repellency was measured using the formula below,

$$\% \text{ Mosquito repellency} = \frac{(\text{NES} + \text{NDE})}{\text{NEX}} \times 100$$

where NES = the number of mosquitoes escaped,

NDE = the number of mosquitoes dead and

NEX = the number of mosquitoes exposed.

The observations collected and further processed in ANOVA software for final results. Almost all textile materials are subjected to washing; so the wash durability can be according to AATCC61 and AATCC143 standards.

8. Insect repellent finishing on textiles

8.1 *Micro-encapsulation method pad-dry-cure technique*

Microcapsules could be spherically formed, whereas some others are unsymmetrical and variably formed, with an amount of smaller droplets of core material inserted throughout the microcapsule. Three different states of matter viz., solids, liquids, and gases could be micro-encapsulated. The controlled release of active ingredients from the capsule depends on the density, permeability and biological properties of the polymeric wall. Mechanical stimuli, chemical stimuli, thermal stimuli and diffusion are four mechanisms for releasing the core materials from the encapsulation. The material that is utilized for encasing the core can be termed as the wall material, shell, membrane, or coating. Microcapsules might have single wall or multiple walls of variable thicknesses around the core material [52]. DEET is one of the best insect repellent and it gradually released from the microcapsule. DEET microcapsules repels, inhibits blood-feeding and kills mosquitoes for a period of at least 6 months. Baker and coworkers have filed a patent on mosquito repellent band comprising micro-encapsulated DEET [53].

Micro-encapsulation effectively used in industries such as pharma, food, perfumery, and textile. In textile industry, it can be used for some wet processing such as dyeing, printing, and finishing.

8.2 *Cyclodextrin applications*

Cyclodextrin gives superior textile finishing to various fabrics such as cotton, cotton blends, and other fabrics. A wash-resistant, and insect-resistant, acrylic fiber with durability of >20 washes was developed by treating fibers with beta-cyclodextrin, isobornyl thiocynoacetate, and siloxane. Insecticides such as permethrin and bioallethrin were incorporated into the cyclodextrins cavity of the modified cotton fabrics. The results showed that the loading of insecticide on the finished fabrics increased with the increase in the quantity of cyclodextrin which subsequently accelerates the repellent action against mosquitoes. Limonene was incorporated in the cavity of cyclodextrin attached with cotton fabrics via monochlorotriazinyl (MCT- β -CD) [54].

9. Conclusions

The use of cyclodextrins in the textile industry has been enhanced. CDs furnish unusual functional properties. CDs form inclusion complexes hence successfully applied for skin-care substances, bioactive substances such as biocides, insecticides, and drugs. Along with these applications CD's potentially used in manufacturing of value added textiles.

References:

- [1] Jinkun Wang, Kuanjun Fang, Xiuming Liu, Shuai Zhang, Xiran Qiao, Dongdong Liu, "A review on the status of formaldehyde-free anti-wrinkle cross-linking agents for cotton fabrics: Mechanisms and applications", *Industrial Crops and Products*, **Part B** (2023), 116831, doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2023.116831
- [2] Lisha Zhang, Man Yui Leung, Svetlana Boriskina, Xiaoming Tao, "Advancing life cycle sustainability of textiles through technological innovations", *Nature Sustainability*, **6** (2023), 243, doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-01004-5
- [3] Gizem Ceylan Türkoğlu, Ayşe Merih Sarıışık, Gökhan Erkan, Mehmet Salih Yıkılmaz, Oya Kontart, "Micro-and nano-encapsulation of limonene and permethrin for mosquito repellent finishing of cotton textiles", *Iranian Polymer Journal*, **29** (2020), 321, doi.org/10.1007/s13726-020-00799-4
- [4] Dai, X.; Jin, Z.; Tao, J., "Study on comfort performance of seamless knitted fabric with mosquito-proof fiber", 2019 *12th ISCID*, Hangzhou, China, 14-15 December; Publisher: IEEE, New York, USA, (2019), 163-166, doi.org/10.1109/iscid.2019.00044
- [5] Rehman, J.U., Ali, A., Khan, I.A., "Plant based products: use and development as repellents against mosquitoes: a review", *Fitoterapia*, **95** (2014), 65–74
- [6] European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control [ECDPC]. Climate change http://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/healthtopics/emerging_and_vector-borne_diseases/vector-borne_diseases/Pages/index.aspx
- [7] World Health Organisation (WHO). A global brief on vector-borne diseases; 2014. p.8., http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/111008/1/WHO_DCO_WHD_2014.1_eng.pdf
- [8] Maheswaran R, Sathis S, Ignacimuthu S., "Larvicidal activity of *Leucus aspera* (Willd.) against the larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus* Say. And *Aedes aegypti*", *Int J Integr Biol*, **2(3)** (2008), 21417
- [9] Eisen RJ, Kugeler KJ, Eisen L, Beard CB, Paddock CD, "Tick-Borne Zoonoses in the United States: Persistent and Emerging Threats to Human Health", *ILAR Journal*, **58(3)** (2017) 319–335, doi:10.1093/ilar/ilx005. ISSN 1084-2020
- [10] Rebecca J. Eisen, Kiersten J. Kugeler, Lars Eisen, Charles B. Beard, Christopher D. Paddock, M. D., "Tick-Borne Zoonoses in the United States: Persistent and Emerging Threats to Human Health", *ILAR J.*, **58(3)** (2017) 319–335, doi: 10.1093/ilar/ilx005
- [11] Rosen, William, "Justinian's Flea: Plague, Empire, and the Birth of Europe", Viking Adult, 2007, p. 3. ISBN 978-0-670-03855-8
- [12] Hays, J. N., "The Burdens of Disease: Epidemics and Human Response in Western History", Rutgers University Press. 1998, pp. 58. ISBN 978-0-8135-2528-0
- [13] Clarke P. S., "The natural history of sensitivity to jack jumper ants (Hymenoptera formicidae *Myrmecia pilosula*) in Tasmania", *The Medical Journal of Australia*, **145(11–12)** (1986), 564, doi:10.5694/j.1326-5377.1986.tb139498.x
- [14] Stafford C. T., "Hypersensitivity to fire ant venom", *Annals of Allergy, Asthma & Immunology*, **77(2)** (1996), 87–95, doi: 10.1016/S1081-1206(10)63493-X
- [15] Holme I., "Innovative technologies for high performance textiles", *Coloration Technol*, **123** (2007), 5973, doi.org/10.1111/j.1478-4408.2007.00064.x
- [16] Diaz J. H., "Chemical and plant-based insect repellents: efficacy, safety, and toxicity", *Wilderness Environ Med*, **27** (2016), 153
- [17] Liberato V. Haule, Lutamyo Nambela, "Sustainable application of nanomaterial for finishing of textile material", In *Micro and Nano Technologies, Green Nanomaterials for Industrial Applications*, Elsevier, 2022, Pages 177-206, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-823296-5.00011-3>.
- [18] G. Buchbauer, L. Jirovetz, "Aromatherapy-Use of Fragrances and Essential Oils as Medicaments", *Flavour and Fragrance Journal*, **9** (1994), 217, doi.org/10.1002/ffj.2730090503
- [19] Xiongyi Peng, Muhammad Umer, Md. Nahid Pervez, K.M. Faridul Hasan, Md Ahsan Habib, Md. Shahinoor Islam, Lina Lin, Xiaorong Xiong, Vincenzo Naddeo, Yingjie Cai, "Bio polymers-based microencapsulation technology for sustainable textiles development: A short review", *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, **7** (2023)100349, doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2023.100349
- [20] Elamri A, Zdiri K, Hamdaoui M, Harzallah O, "Chitosan: A biopolymer for textile processes and products", *Textile Research Journal*, **93(5-6)** (2023), 1456, doi: 10.1177/00405175221127315
- [21] Russo, R.; Palla, F., "Plant Essential Oils as Biocides in Sustainable Strategies for the Conservation of Cultural Heritage", *Sustainability*, **15** (2023), 8522, doi.org/10.3390/su15118522
- [22] Michaela Olisha S. Lobregas, Emmanuel Victor D. Buniao, Julius L. Leaño, "Alkali-enzymatic treatment of *Bambusa blumeana* textile fibers for natural fiber-based textile material production", *Industrial Crops and Products*, **194** (2023), 116268, doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2023.116268
- [23] Atwah AA, Khan MA, "Influence of microscopic features on the self-cleaning ability of textile fabrics", *Textile Research Journal*, **93(1-2)** (2023), 450, doi: 10.1177/00405175211069881
- [24] Mickael Maton, Sarah Gabut, Christel Neut, Pascal Odou, Camille Sacareau, Anthony Pinon, Michèle Vialette, Gaétan Gerber, Bernard Martel, Nicolas Blanchemain, "Antiviral functionalization of a polypropylene nonwoven textile structure as a self-decontaminating layer for respiratory masks", *Biomater. Sci*, **11** (2023), 3502, doi.org/10.1039/D2BM01988D
- [25] Escobar, K.; Garrido-Miranda, K.A.; Pulido, R.; Naveas, N.; Manso-Silván, M.; Hernandez-Montelongo, J., "Coatings of Cyclodextrin/Citric-Acid Biopolymer as Drug Delivery Systems: A Review", *Pharmaceutics* **15** (2023), 296, doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15010296

- [26] Mazurek, A.H.; Szeleszczuk, L., “A Review of Applications of Solid-State Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (ssNMR) for the Analysis of Cyclodextrin-Including Systems, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, **24** (2023), 364, doi.org/10.3390/ijms24043648
- [27] Qiuxiang Wang, Aiwen Zhang, Lu Zhu, Xuewen Yang, Guihua Fang, Bo Tang, “Cyclodextrin-based ocular drug delivery systems: A comprehensive review”, *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, **476** (2023), 14919, doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2022.214919
- [28] J. Szejtli, “The properties and potential uses of cyclodextrin derivatives,” *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, **14** (1992), 25, doi.org/10.1007/BF01041363
- [29] G. Wenz, “Superstructures with cyclodextrins: Chemistry and applications II”, *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.* **11** (2015), 271, doi.org/10.3762/bjoc.11.30
- [30] K. Freudenberg, M. Meyer-Delius, “The Schardinger dextrans from starch”, *Ber.* **71B** (1938), 71B, 1596-1600 (CA 32: 8373)
- [31] M. A. Villiers, *Compt. Rend.Chem.*, **112** (1891), 536
- [32] M. Lezcano, W. Ai-Soufi, M. Novo, E. Rodriguez-Nunez, J. V. Tato, “Complexation of several benzimidazole-type fungicides with α - and β -cyclodextrins”, *J. Agric Food Chem*, **50** (2002), 108, https://doi.org/10.1021/jf010927y
- [33] F. Giuseppe, T. Carmen, G. Carmine, D. R. Margherita, C. Ugo, N. Placido, R. Antonio, “ γ -Cyclodextrin as a catalyst for the synthesis of 2-methyl-3, 5-diarylisoxazolines in water”, *J. Org. Chem.*, **82** (2017), 4631, https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.joc.7b00227
- [34] Y. Xu, A. K. Rashwan, A. I. Osman, E. M. Abd El-Monaem, A. M. Elgarahy, A. S. Eltaweil, M. Omar, Y. Li, A-H E. Mehanni, W. Chen, D. W. Rooney, “Synthesis and potential applications of cyclodextrin-based metal-organic frameworks: a review:”, *Environ Chem Lett.*, **21** (2023), 447, doi.org/10.1007/s10311-022-01509-7
- [35] Zongjian Liu, Lin Ye, Jianing Xi, Jin Wang, Zeng-guo Feng, “Cyclodextrin polymers: Structure, synthesis, and use as drug carriers”, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **118** (2021), 101408, doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2021.101408
- [36] A. A-H Abdellatif, F. Ahmed, A. M Mohammed, M. Alsharidah, A. Al-Subaiyel, W. A Samman, A. A Alhaddad, S. Hamad Al-Mijalli, M. A Amin, H. Barakat, S. K Osman, “Recent Advances in the Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Applications of Cyclodextrin-Capped Gold Nanoparticles”, *Int J Nanomedicine*, **14** (18) (2023), 3247-3281, doi:10.2147/IJN.S405964
- [37] Yadav, M., Thakore, S., Jadeja, R., “A review on remediation technologies using functionalized Cyclodextrin”, *Environ Sci Pollut Res.*, **29** (2022), 236, doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-15887-y
- [38] X. Zhang, C. Huang, J. Ren, T. G. Bekele, H. Zhao, “Effect of cyclodextrin on desorption of petroleum hydrocarbons in soil”, *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, **160** (2022), 199, doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2022.02.023
- [39] [Internet] Insect Repellent Market Outlook Report - Market Size, Market Split, Market Shares Data, Insights, Trends, Opportunities, Companies: Growth Forecasts by Product Type, Application, and Region from 2022 to 2030. https://www.researchandmarkets.com/report/insect-repellent
- [40] A. Al Parvez, Md. J. Hossain, Md. Z. Hossain, M. S. H. Sohan, F. Hoque, Md. H. Ahsan, Md. S. Hoquef, “Mosquito repellent fabric: Development and characterization of peppermint and garlic mixture finish on knitted fabric to examine mosquito repellency”, *Heliyon.*, **9**(5) (2023), e15944, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon. 2023.e15944
- [41] E. J. Norris, J. R. Coats, “Current and Future Repellent Technologies: The Potential of Spatial Repellents and Their Place in Mosquito-Borne Disease Control”, *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, **14**(2) 2017, 124, doi: 10.3390/ijerph14020124
- [42] Press Release, Published May 3, 2023, “Body Worn Insect Repellent Market Demand by 2031”, https://www.digitaljournal.com/pr/news/theexpresswire/body-worn-insect-repellent-market-demand-by-2031#ixzz8511hys00”
- [43] Margaret Brown, MD, Adelaide A. Hebert, MD, “Insect repellents: An overview”, *Journal of American Academy of Dermatology*, **36**(2) (1997), 243, doi.org/10.1016/S0190-9622 (97)70289-5
- [44] P. J. Robbins, M. G. Cherniack, “Review of the biodistribution and toxicity of the insect repellent N, N-diethyl-m-toluamide (DEET)”, *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health*, **18**(4) (1986), 503, doi:10.1080/15287398609530891
- [45] A thesis submitted by Kalapurakkal S M., “Exposure of children to DEET and othertopically applied repellents”, *Master Public Health* (2005), https://www.studocu.com/ph/document/sti-west-negros-university/science/umi-umd-2419-research/27444797
- [46] Edwards J W, Lee S G, Heath L M, Pisaniello D L, “Worker exposure and a risk assessment of Malathion and fenthion used in the control of Mediterranean fruit fly in South Australia”, *Environ Res.*, **103**(1) (2007), 3845, doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2006.06.001
- [47] A. S. Estep, N. D. Sanscrainte, C. M. Waits, S. J. Bernard, A. M. Lloyd, K. J. Lucas, E. A. Buckner, R. Vaidyanathan, R. Morreale, L. A. Conti, J. J. Becnel, “Quantification of permethrin resistance and kdr alleles in Florida strains of *Aedes aegypti* (L.) and *Aedes albopictus* (Skuse)”, *PLoS PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, **12**(10) (2018), e0006544, doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0006544
- [48] D. O. Freedman, L. H. Weld, P. E. Kozarsky, T. Fisk, R. Robins, F. von Sonnenburg, J. S. Keystone, P. Pandey, M. S. Cetron, “Spectrum of disease and relation to place of exposure among ill returned travelers”, *The New England Journal of Medicine*, **354**(2) (2006), 11930, doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa051331
- [49] J. Islam, K. Zaman, S. Duarah, P. S. Raju, P. Chattopadhyay, “Mosquito repellents: An insight into the chronological perspectives and novel discoveries”, *Acta Tropica*, **167** (2017), 216-230, doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2016.12.031

- [50] Vincent Corbel 1, Maria Stankiewicz, Cédric Pennetier, Didier Fournier, Jure Stojan, Emmanuelle Girard, Mitko Dimitrov, Jordi Molgó, Jean-Marc Hougard, Bruno Lapied, “Evidence for inhibition of cholinesterases in insect and mammalian nervous systems by the insect repellent DEET”, *BMC Biol.*, **5(7)** (2009) 47, doi.org/10.1186/1741-7007-7-47
- [51] Maia M. F., Moore S.J., “Plant-based insect repellents: a review of their efficacy, development and testing”, *Malaria Journal*, **10(Suppl 1)** (2011), S11, doi.org/10.1186/1475-2875-10-S1-S11
- [52] D. M Soderlund, J. M Clark, L. P Sheets, L. S Mullin, V. J Piccirillo, D. Sargent, J. T Stevens, M. L Weiner, “Mechanisms of pyrethroid neurotoxicity: Implications for cumulative risk assessment”, *Toxicology*, **171 (1)**, (2002), 359, doi: 10.1016/s0300-483x(01)00569-8
- [53] Madene A, Jacquot M, Scher J, Desobry S., “Flavour encapsulation and controlled release—a review”, *Int J Food Sci Technol.*, **41** (2006), 121
- [54] Nasanjargal Purev, Ladislav Burgert, Petr Prichystal, Radim Hrdina, Jiri Kühn, Michal Cerny, Jamyan Oyuntulkuur, “Dyeing of leather with microencapsulated acid dye”, *Color Technol*, **129(6)** (2013), 41217, doi:10.1111/cote.12054